

Results including trendlines

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| Software for HCPs_LR | Software for HCPs_CT | Social media and communication platforms_LR |
| Social media and communication platforms_CT | Intervention_LR | Intervention_CT |
| Internet_LR | Internet_CT | Insulin administration system_LR |
| Insulin administration system_CT | Hardware and devices_LR | Hardware and devices_CT |
| Glucose monitor_LR | Glucose monitor_CT | General_LR |
| General_CT | Closed system and artificial pancreas_LR | Closed system and artificial pancreas_CT |
| Biomarkers and complementary medical techniques_LR | Biomarkers and complementary medical techniques_CT | Assessment_LR |
| Assessment_CT | Applications_LR | Applications_CT |
| Algorithm_LR | Algorithm_CT | AI-based system_LR |
| AI-based system_CT | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Software for HCPs_LR) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Social media and communication platforms_LR) |
| 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Social media and communication platforms_CT) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Intervention_LR) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Internet_LR) |
| 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Internet_CT) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Insulin administration system_LR) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Insulin administration system_CT) |
| 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Hardware and devices_LR) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Hardware and devices_LR) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Glucose monitor_LR) |
| 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Glucose monitor_CT) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (General_LR) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (General_CT) |
| 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Closed system and artificial pancreas_LR) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Closed system and artificial pancreas_CT) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Biomarkers and complementary medical techniques_LR) |
| 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Biomarkers and complementary medical techniques_CT) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Assessment_LR) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Assessment_CT) |
| 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Applications_LR) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Applications_CT) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Algorithm_LR) |
| 2 per. Mov. Avg. (Algorithm_CT) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (AI-based system_LR) | 2 per. Mov. Avg. (AI-based system_CT) |

Frequencies

- Insulin administration system_LR
- AI-based system_LR
- Software for HCPs_LR
- General_LR
- Internet_LR
- Glucose monitor_CT
- Applications_CT
- Biomarkers and complementary medical techniques_CT
- Intervention_CT
- Glucose monitor_LR
- Applications_LR
- Biomarkers and complementary medical techniques_LR
- Intervention_LR
- Algorithm_LR
- Closed system and artificial pancreas_LR
- Social media and communication platforms_LR
- Hardware and devices_LR
- Assessment_LR
- Insulin administration system_CT
- AI-based system_CT
- Software for HCPs_CT
- General_CT
- Internet_CT
- Algorithm_CT
- Closed system and artificial pancreas_CT
- Social media and communication platforms_CT
- Hardware and devices_CT
- Assessment_CT

ZOOMED - Frequencies

- Insulin administration system_LR
- AI-based system_LR
- Software for HCPs_LR
- General_LR
- Internet_LR
- Glucose monitor_CT
- Applications_CT
- Biomarkers and complementary medical techniques_CT
- Intervention_CT
- Algorithm_CT
- Glucose monitor_LR
- Applications_LR
- Biomarkers and complementary medical techniques_LR
- Intervention_LR
- Algorithm_LR
- Closed system and artificial pancreas_LR
- Social media and communication platforms_LR
- Hardware and devices_LR
- Assessment_LR
- Insulin administration system_CT
- AI-based system_CT
- Software for HCPs_CT
- General_CT
- Internet_CT

Time period use of Keywords

Zoomed – time period use of keywords

